

Endodontic Management Of Mandibular Second Molar With C-Shaped Canal Configuration: A Case Series

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Abstract :

Anatomical variations in root canal morphology, particularly in mandibular molars, continue to present significant challenges in endodontic diagnosis and treatment. Among these, mandibular second molars often exhibit root fusion, resulting in complex and atypical canal configurations. A well-recognized variation is the C-shaped root canal system, characterized by a fin- or web-like connection between canals, producing a distinct C-shaped cross-sectional outline. This configuration may persist as a continuous ribbon-shaped canal throughout the root or bifurcate into separate canals toward the apex.

Conventional radiographs often fail to reveal such complexities, making accurate diagnosis reliant on a combination of clinical expertise, detailed examination of the pulpal floor, and advanced imaging modalities such as cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT). The adjunctive use of magnification, such as a dental operating microscope, further enhances visualization, thereby facilitating precise negotiation, thorough debridement, and effective obturation of these challenging canal systems.

This case report presents the successful endodontic management of a mandibular second molar with a C-shaped canal configuration using magnification, tailored instrumentation, and obturation techniques. It underscores the importance of comprehensive morphological assessment and individualized treatment planning in achieving predictable outcomes in cases with anatomical complexities.

Keywords: Anatomic variation, C-shaped canal, Mandibular second molar, Root canal morphology, Cone- beam computed tomography (CBCT).

Introduction:

A thorough understanding of root canal anatomy and its variations is crucial for the success of endodontic therapy. Among posterior teeth, mandibular second molars are well- documented for their morphological complexity, with C-shaped root canal systems representing one of the most challenging anatomical variations encountered in clinical practice. These configurations arise due to the failure of Hertwig's epithelial root sheath to fuse on the lingual or buccal aspect during root development, resulting in a longitudinal groove and a characteristic C-shaped cross-sectional morphology [1].

C-shaped canal first reported by Cooke and Cox in 1979, C-shaped canals are most commonly found in mandibular second molars, with reported prevalence ranging from 2.7% to over 40%, depending on ethnic and geographic variations [2], [3]. These canal systems often present with a single, ribbon-like orifice at the chamber floor that may persist throughout the root or divide into two or more canals apically [4]. Their complex internal anatomy, including fins, isthmuses, and intercanal communications, significantly complicates debridement, shaping, and obturation [5].

Melton et al's classification describes the following three types of C shaped canals continuous C shaped (C1), semicolon (C2) and separate canals (C3). This classification was further modified by Fan et al and the most prevalent type of C shape canal was single orifice with an uninterrupted "C" shape configuration according to this classification.[2,3]

Therefore, the use of Cone-Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT) plays a vital role in the accurate diagnosis and assessment of the canal configuration [6]. In addition, magnification aids are invaluable in locating and treating these complex canal systems [7].

A combination of rotary and hand instrumentation, copious irrigation, and thermoplasticized obturation techniques is often necessary to achieve a favorable outcome [8]. This case report presents the endodontic treatment of a mandibular second molar with a confirmed C-shaped root canal morphology, emphasizing modified clinical protocols in successfully managing such anatomical variations.

Case 1:

A 45 year old male patient reported to the department of conservative dentistry and endodontics with the chief complaint of spontaneous pain and sensitivity in the lower left back tooth region for the past one week. Clinical examination revealed deep occlusal caries in the mandibular left second molar (tooth #37) with tenderness on vertical percussion. Pulp vitality tests (cold and electric pulp test) elicited a lingering pain response, indicative of irreversible pulpitis.

Preoperative periapical radiograph as shown in Fig.1. Tooth was conical in shape with fused mesial and distal roots and a thin radiolucent line between them, with a suspected C-shaped canal. Based on clinical and radiographic findings, nonsurgical root canal treatment was planned .

Local anesthesia (2% lidocaine with 1:100,000 epinephrine) was administered, and rubber dam isolation was performed. After access cavity preparation, two C-shaped canal orifices was observed on the pulp chamber floor. Canal negotiation was performed using ISO #10 and #15 K-files under magnification. Working length was determined using an apex locator and verified radiographically as shown in Fig. 3.

Cleaning and shaping were carried out using a hybrid technique combining hand instrumentation and rotary NiTi files, with copious irrigation using 5.25% sodium hypochlorite and 17% EDTA. The canal was dried with paper points, master cone radiograph was taken as shown in Fig. 3. and obturation was completed using sectional obturation and warm vertical compaction technique and bioceramic sealer as shown in Fig. 4. The access cavity was restored with composite resin. The patient was asymptomatic at the 1-week and 1-month follow-up visits.

Figures :

Fig. 1 Pre-operative IOPA X-ray with 37 photograph

Access opening photograph

Fig. 2 Working length determination with 37

Fig. 3 Master cone with 37

Fig. 4 Post-operative IOPA X-ray with 37

Case 2

A 36 year old female patient reported to the department with a chief complaint of pain on eating food in lower left back region of the tooth. No relevant medical history was present to the patient. Intraoral examination revealed carious # 37 with tenderness on percussion. Radiographically, radiolucency was seen in tooth 37 closely approximating the pulp space along with an associated widening of periodontal ligament space. Tooth was conical in shape with fused mesial and distal roots and a thin radiolucent line between them joining at apical one third, with a suspected C-shaped canal.

Local anesthesia (2% lidocaine with 1:100,000 epinephrine) was administered, and rubber dam isolation was performed. After access cavity preparation, two-C-shaped canal orifices was observed on the pulp chamber floor. Canal negotiation was performed using ISO #10 and #15 K-files under magnification. Working length was determined using an apex locator and verified radiographically as shown in Fig. 2.

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Discussion:

C-shaped canals are recognized as one of the most complex and challenging endodontic anatomies to treat, particularly due to their variable internal morphology and high prevalence in mandibular second molars [1]. Root fusion is the underlying cause of this configuration, leading to an irregular, fin-like canal that may harbor multiple ramifications and isthmuses that are difficult to clean and fill effectively [2].

The diagnosis of a C-shaped canal was initially suspected on radiographs and later confirmed with cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT). The three-dimensional assessment provided by CBCT proved crucial for evaluating the canal configuration and curvature[3]. Patel et al. highlighted the indispensable role of CBCT in identifying such complex anatomies that often remain undetected on conventional radiographs [6].

The cleaning and shaping of C-shaped canals remain particularly challenging due to their irregular cross-sections, isthmuses, webs, and fins, which can retain pulp tissue and bacteria. Preoperative radiographs frequently reveal fused roots; therefore, additional angulated views at approximately 20° mesially or distally can aid in recognizing this configuration. During preparation, isthmus enlargement should be limited up to a size 25 file, and anticurvature filing is recommended to minimize the risk of strip perforation [4].

Effective irrigation, preferably supplemented with ultrasonic activation, is considered essential for debriding inaccessible areas within this complex anatomy. [5,6]. Jafarzadeh and Wu emphasized that conventional rotary instrumentation alone is often inadequate, and a combination of hand files with activated irrigation is required for thorough debridement [7]. In the present case, a hybrid instrumentation approach, along with copious irrigation and the use of EDTA, was employed to optimize canal disinfection.

For obturation, a thermoplasticized technique was selected, as it provides a superior three-dimensional seal compared to cold lateral compaction [8]. A large plugger was positioned over one of the seared master cones, while a smaller plugger was used to down-pack the other, ensuring complete and homogenous filling of the intricate canal system.[9,10]

Conclusion :

C-shaped root canal systems represent a significant endodontic challenge due to their complex and variable internal anatomy. Successful management of such configurations requires a comprehensive understanding of root canal morphology, along with the integration of advanced diagnostic tools like CBCT and clinical aids such as magnification. This case underscores the importance of early identification, meticulous cleaning, and an individualized obturation approach in achieving optimal clinical outcomes. A tailored treatment strategy, informed by detailed anatomical assessment, is essential for the long-term success of endodontic therapy in teeth with C-shaped canal configurations.

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